

**REFLECTIONS AT THE “HOUSE OF THE SERBIAN QUEEN”
(NATALIA OBRENOVIC – CHISINAU – PUSHKIN
*Размышления у «Дома сербской королевы»
(Наталья Обренович – Кишинев – Пушкин)***

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Summary. Chisinau hides many secrets. The old mansions can tell about the secrets of the past. In one of them once lived a woman who was called the most beautiful and most unfortunate queen of Europe - Natalia Obrenovic. A. S. Pushkin met representatives of the family of Natalia Obrenovic and her husband, King Milon I Obrenovic, during his stay in Chisinau in 1821–1823. He sketched some of them on the sheets of his Chisinau manuscripts, which has important documentary and historical significance. The purpose of this article is to create a schematic genealogy of Natalia Keshko and Milon I Obrenovic, to more clearly present their relationship as second cousins. In working on this topic, the author relies on the works of famous scientists: G. Bezzvikonny, E. Dvoichenko-Markova and others, as well as on Pushkin's drawings. Methods of observation, comparison, synthesis, analysis and others will help solve the problem.

Key words: Chisinau, Serbia, Natalia Obrenovic, genealogy, Pushkin's drawings.

Chisinau holds many mysteries. The most eloquent way to tell about the secrets of the past can be found in old mansions, which would not be ashamed to be moved to the square of any of the European capitals. On Lazo Street, 34 there is such a mansion – an architectural monument of national importance, included in the register of historical and cultural monuments of Chisinau. If old walls could talk, we would learn many interesting stories, sad and happy, that we don't even know about. The history of the “House of the Serbian Queen” (the name of the author of the article) began in 1858, with the date of its construction, which is preserved on the pediment of the building.

The wife of a collegiate councilor, Elizaveta Laurent, purchased a plot of land (approximately 4,000 square meters) from the City Duma, where a luxurious house with eleven rooms was built in the Turkish Empire style (according to a project approved by the Construction and Road Commission of 1857).

The house was located in the depths of a huge garden, away from the noisy streets. After some time, it was sold to Prince Mihail A. Cantacuzino. Then it became the property of the family of Ion Keshko and his wife Zamfira Keshko, née Kazimir, who were often visited by their granddaughter Natalia Keshko, the future Queen of Serbia. Later, the house became the property of Maria Hasnash, and in 1899–Ida Shpirt.

Fig. 1. House of Natalia Obrenovic. <https://bloknot-moldova.ru/news/dramaticheskaya-sud-ba-korolevy-skazalas-na-ee-kish-918367>

Natalia Obrenovic (née Natalia Petrovna Keshko; 1859–1941) – wife of King Milan I of Serbia, Princess Consort of Serbia from 1875 to 1882, Queen Consort of Serbia from 1882 to 1889, Queen Mother of Serbia from 1889 to 1903.¹ Natalia Keshko was born in Florence into the family of the largest Bessarabian landowner Pyotr Ivanovich Keshko (a descendant of one of the branches of the Vasilko family), a colonel in the Russian service, and the Moldavian princess Pulcheria (Profira) Sturdza (1805–1887; from the Moldavian boyar family of Sturdza, granddaughter of the Moldavian ruler Ionița Sandu Sturdza).

Natalia was always proud of and emphasized her high aristocratic origin. On her father's side, Natalia inherited a rich and distinguished pedigree from the boyar families of Balsh, Manolaki, Paladi, Callimachi, and Catarji. On her mother's side, she was connected to the powerful boyar families of Cantacuzino-Deleanu, Moruzi, Ghica-Comanesti, Sturdza, Rosseti-Raducan, who represented the political power structures and were the highest aristocratic elite of Bessarabia. Pulcheria Nikolaevna Keshko's sisters were Ekaterina Sturdza (married Princess Muruzi) and Zoya Sturdza (married Cantacuzina).

Members of the noble families of Sturdza and Moruzi became rulers of Moldova. Pulcheria, Natalia's mother, played the piano beautifully and was famous for her beauty and intelligence. The French poet Edouard Grenier was in love with her.² Natalia's grandfather, Ivan (Ion) Keshko (1831, Chisinau–1865), was a member of the Supreme Council of Bessarabia and the leader of the nobility of the Chisinau and Orhei, and then Iasi and Soroca districts. His first marriage was to Natalia, the daughter of the great logothet Iordaki Balsh;

¹ *Natalia, Queen of Serbia*. Brockhaus and Efron Encyclopedic Dictionary. In 86 volumes (82 volumes and 4 add.). St. Petersburg, 1890–1907.

² George Bezviconi, *Boierimea Moldovei dintre Prut și Nistru*, Bucuresti, 1940, vol. I, pp. 33-181; George Bezviconi, *Boierimea Moldovei dintre Prut și Nistru*, Bucuresti, 1943, vol. II, p. 13, 15, 17, 19, 84, 85, 181, 193, 202.

his second marriage was to Zamfira Yegorovna Kalmutskaya (1819–1881). Natalia's father, Keshko Petr Ivanovich (1831, Chisinau – 1865), served as a lieutenant in the Yerevan Hussar Regiment. During the Crimean War, he was an adjutant to General Gorchakov and was friends with the famous physician Dmitry Krupensky.

The Keshko family with their children (Ekaterina, née Ghica; Maria, née Ghica; Ivan and Natalia, née Obrenovic) lived in Florence for long periods of time because of the warm climate, which was favorable for Pulcheria, who suffered from tuberculosis.

Natalia received an aristocratic upbringing, an excellent home education, and spoke several foreign languages. But the happiness of this family did not last long. Natalia's father died suddenly at the age of 35 (when she was only 6 years old), and 9 years later her mother died. A fifteen-year-old orphan with a huge dowry, by that time had turned into a real beauty.

After the early death of her father, Natalia was raised in the family of relatives Ekaterina and Constantin Moruzi (owners of the estate of Danutseny near Ungheni), who, together with her grandmother, took care of Natalia with special warmth.

Natalia often traveled to Chisinau, Iasi, Odessa, Vienna. In Chisinau, she stayed in the house of her beloved relatives, grandparents, Ion and Zamfira Keshko. During one of her trips to Vienna, Natalia met her future husband – Serbian prince Milan Obrenovic, the future king of Serbia Milan I.

Milan Obrenović was born in 1854 in exile in Moldova, in the small town of Marasesti, near Iași, to Milos Obrenović and Elena-Maria Katarža (known in Serbia as Marija Obrenović). Elena-Maria Katarža was the daughter of Moldovan boyars Constantin and Smaranda (Esmeralda) Katarža, née Balš (1811–1886). Smaranda (Esmeralda) Katarža was the daughter of Iordachi Balš (1776–1849) and Roxanda Balš, née Sturdza.

Soon after his birth, his parents divorced. Two years later, at the age of 7, Milan lost his father, who died in battle with the Turks near Bucharest. His mother, Elena Maria, received custody, but soon became the mistress of the ruler Alexandru Ioan Cuza (with whom she had two more sons). Young Milan was adopted by Mihail Obrenovic, a cousin of Milos Obrenovic. Smaranda (Esmeralda) Balsh's sister was Natalia, née Balsh (1812–1830), married to Ion Keshko, who had a son, Peter. Peter Ivanovich Keshko (1830–1865), a colonel in the Russian army, and his wife, Pulcheria Nikolaevna Keshko, née Princess Sturdza (1831–1874), became the parents of the future first Queen of Serbia, Natalia Obrenovic, née Keshko (1859–1941). She was named Natalia in honor of her grandmother, who died early.

It was because of these family ties that Milan I and Natalia were second cousins, since Elena-Maria, née Katarzhi, and Petr Ivanovich Keshko were first cousins born of full sisters. His mother, Elena-Maria Katarzhi, was a first cousin of Natalia's father, Petr Keshko, so Milan spoke excellent Romanian from childhood.³

The sympathy that flared up between the young people was supported by relatives on both sides, who were trying to arrange the lives of their children in the most advantageous way. He was a representative of the ruling dynasty, she was a rich bride. The family ties of this couple did not bother anyone, they were considered quite common among the Balkan aristocracy of that time, largely isolated from the outside world.

In Vienna in October 1875, Milan I, aged 21, married 16-year-old Natalia Balsh. They were married in the Belgrade Cathedral. In 1876, they had a son, Aleksandar I Obrenovic,

³ George Bezviconi, *Arhondologia Basarabiei. Boierii Balș*, Chișinău: Din trecutul nostru, 1934, № 7-8, pp. 16-18; Chișinău: Din trecutul nostru, 1935, № 25-27, p. 26; Chișinău: Din trecutul nostru, 1939, October, p. 38.

Fig. 2. Elena-Maria Katarzhi <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>

Fig. 3. Milan Obrenovic. <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/>

Fig. 4. Natalia Obrenovic. <https://ru-royalty.livejournal.com/3310940.html>

the future last king of Serbia (who was already ethnically 3/4 Moldavian). In her marriage with Milan, Natalia had two sons: Aleksandar and Sergej (who died a few days after his birth in 1878).

In 1882, Prince Milan proclaimed Serbia a kingdom, and Natalia became Queen of Serbia. In 1888, the couple divorced. Five years later, in 1893, they reconciled and asked the church to annul their divorce. In 1889, after King Milan abdicated, Milan and Natalia's son, Alexander I, became King of Serbia. In 1900, a serious conflict arose between father and son Obrenović over Alexander I's marriage to Draga Mašin, a maid of honor at the Obrenović court who had already been married. Five years later, King Alexander I and his wife Draga Mašin were brutally murdered.

Queen Natalia remained the only representative of the Obrenović dynasty. She donated her fortune to the University of Belgrade, Serbian churches and monasteries and converted to Catholicism; in 1903 she took monastic vows. Natalia spent the rest of her life in France, died in 1941 in Saint-Denis and was buried in the cemetery in the village of Lardy (37 km from Paris). Her unpublished memoirs are kept in the Vatican archives.

Once she wrote about her death: "This will be... the beginning of my happiness..."⁴

At the beginning of the 19th century, revolutions took place in Spain, Portugal, Naples, and Piedmont. Having been exiled to Bessarabia (1820–1823), A. S. Pushkin found himself at the center of European upheavals. It was at this time, after the beginning of the Serbian Uprising and the Greek Revolution, that Kishinev was filled with noble princes and noble boyars from Moldova, Wallachia, Serbia, Greece, and other Balkan countries. In an official report dated May 11, 1821, the Bessarabian governor I.N. Inzov reported the details: "Almost all the Moldavian boyars left for us and some for Austria."⁵

⁴ Lilia Zabolotnaia, *Молдавские социальные элиты в истории Сербии. Страницы из истории брака Наталии Кешко и Милана Обреновича*, Uploaded (2021), in: *Balcanica Posnaniensia. Acta et studia*, p. 24.

⁵ I. Iovva, *Southern Decembrists and the Greek National Liberation Movement*, Chisinau, 1963, p. 34.

According to A.F. Veltman, “In every house... there lived settlers from the magnificent chambers of Iasi and Bucharest.”⁶ This gave Pushkin the opportunity to come into closer contact with the characteristic and outstanding representatives of Serbia, Greece, Moldova and Wallachia, some of whom have firmly entered the history of these countries.⁷

Fig. 5. Part of the Keshko-Balsh family tree. Compiled by V. Grabovscaia.

One of the most open houses in Chisinau was the house of Smaragda Bogdan, née Rosetti (1770–1847). She was the wife of Dimitrie Bogdan, falsely accused and executed by Prince Constantin Moruzi in 1778. This execution caused open indignation among the population of Moldova and left its mark on national folklore. Smaranda Bogdan had a beautiful daughter – Maria (Margiolitsa) Balsh, née Bogdan – one of the most brilliant representatives of Iassian society in the first half of the 19th century. The historical novel by Dumitru Almasi “Aleii, codrule firtate!” depicted the images of Smaranda Bogdan and Maria Balsh.⁸

Todor Balsh and his brother Iordache arrived in Chisinau among other boyars along with their families. In addition to Todor Balsh and his wife, A.S. Pushkin knew his brother George (Iordache) and his family well: his wife (second) Anica Filipescu (daughter of the Grand Visternik of the Wallachian Principality) and children – Alexander (? – 22.2.1847); Smaranda (1811–1886; married to the Grand Logothete Costin Katardzhi), Natalia (1812–1830; married to the leader of the nobility of Bessarabia Ioan Keshko), Profira, Panait (1817–1889).

⁶ A.F. Veltman, *Bessarabian Memories of Pushkin*. In the book: L.N Maikov. Pushkin, St. Petersburg, 1899, pp. 117-118.

⁷ V. Grosul, *Serbian Colonies in Bessarabia in the 19th Century*, M: Bulletin of Slavic Cultures, 2022, pp. 16-17.

⁸ Dumitru Almasi, *Aleii, codrule firtate!* Bucharest, 1956; E.M. Dvoichenko-Markova, *Pushkin in Moldova and Wallachia*, Moscow, 1979, pp. 49-51.

Fig. 6. Tombstone of Victoria Inglesi. <https://chisinaurasulmeu.com/>

Fig. 7. The Balsh-Keshko family: Tudor and Smaranda Balsh, Iordache Balsh, Alexander (Aleko) Balsh and others. A. S. From the: A. S. Pushkin, *The First Kishinev Workbook*, Pushkin House, 831, p. 33, reverse. April 11, 1821. Definition by G. F. Bogach.

An excerpt from a letter from Alexander Balsh to Pushkin in French has been preserved: “How can I find you? A. Balsh” (1821–1823). The original letter - a material monument of Pushkin’s acquaintance with Alexander Balsh – is in the Pushkin House in St. Petersburg.⁹

In Kishinev lived Tarsis Mikhailovna Keshko, “a fifty-year-old widow” (Druganov by her second husband) and her daughter – Victoria Ivanovna Vakar (née Keshko), the wife of Lieutenant Colonel of the Okhotsk Infantry Regiment Filipp Grigorievich Vakar. According to I. P. Liprandi, Pushkin often visited Tarsis Keshko to eat “dulchatsu” (jam), and he loved to dance with Victoria.¹⁰ The Keshko family also produced the “Kishinev Juliet”, Victoria Inglesi-Keshko, whose marble tombstone was located in the Armenian Cemetery.

Victoria Keshko was born in Chisinau in 1835. Her brother was Peter Keshko, the father of Natalia Obrenovic, the Serbian queen, so she was Natalia’s aunt. The girl received an excellent education in Odessa and then in Vienna. In 1854, she met Maximilian (1832–1867), a 22-year-old Austrian prince from the Habsburg dynasty. commander-in-chief of the Austrian fleet.

The young people fell in love, but the Archduke could not marry a simple noblewoman. Victoria’s mother, Zemfira Yegorovna Keshko, took her daughter back to her homeland, where she was married to landowner Alexander Dmitrievich Inglezi. The wedding took place in Odessa. In 1856, the young couple had a daughter. Three months after the birth of the child, Victoria Inglezi fell ill with a severe cold and died. She was only 21 years old.

⁹ M.A. Tsyavlovsky, *Chronicle of the life and work of A. S. Pushkin*, M.: Publishing House of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1951, p. 300.

¹⁰ L.F. Chereisky, *Pushkin and his entourage*, L.: Nauka, 1989, p. 58, 190.

Fig. 8. Smaranda Bogdan. From the: București, Collection of portraits of the Romanian Academy, 1938, Vol. I, p. 220.

Fig. 9. Smaranda Bogdan and Maria Balsh. From the: A.S. Pushkin, The First Kishinev Workbook, Pushkin House, 831, p. 61, reverse, 1821. Definition by V. Grabovscaia

Maximilian, apparently for political purposes, married his second cousin, the Belgian princess Charlotte. With the support of the French Emperor Napoleon III, Maximilian received the title and crown of Emperor of Mexico. And in 1867, he was shot by Mexican rebels, which shocked Europe. This event was captured in his painting “The Execution of Emperor Maximilian” by the French artist Edouard Manet.

Of the Inglezi family, Pushkin was acquainted in Chisinau with the gypsy Lyudmila Inglezi-Shekora (1802–1825). According to unreliable information, Pushkin’s relationship with Lyudmila was reflected in the plot of the poem “The Gypsies”.¹¹

But the conflict that ended with a challenge to a duel between Dmitry Inglezi (a major Greek merchant, mayor of Odessa; 1771–1846) and Pushkin did take place. The reason was that Inglezi was jealous of the young gypsy Lyudmila Shekora. But the duel did not take place thanks to the wise decision of Governor-General Inzov, who placed Pushkin under house arrest, and handed Inglezi a ticket with “permission to travel abroad.”¹²

Of all the children of D. Inglezi, the most famous was his son Alexander Dmitrievich Inglezi (1826–1903), who acquired the village of Tataresti in Orhei district and became the largest tobacco producer in Bessarabia. Serbian-Moldavian ties go back many centuries and date back to the Middle Ages. The same can be said about the genealogy of A.S. Pushkin. The Pushkin noble family dates back to the 12th century.

It is interesting to note that the legendary ancestor of the ancient noble family of the Pushkins, Ratsha, was a native of the city of Petrovaradin, and by nationality, a Serb. He ar-

¹¹ L.F. Chereisky, *Pushkin and his entourage*, L.: Nauka, 1989, p. 172.

¹² S. Petrov, *Dmitry Inglezi: a forgotten name*, Spring Odessa, 1973.

rived in Rus' from Serbia through "Sedmigradje", that is, Transylvania, and served the Grand Duke Alexander Neavsky.¹³

This is confirmed by the coat of arms of the Pushkin family, included in the General Armorial of the noble families of the Russian Empire. In the upper part of the shield is a princely cap (reminding that Ratsha served the Grand Duke Alexander Nevsky). In the lower part is a hand with a sword in silver armor (ancient Slavonian emblem of the descendants of Ratsha). In the left field, an eagle holds a sword and orb in its claws (the eagle is the family coat of arms of the ancestors of Ratsha). The shield is topped with a noble helmet, a crown and three ostrich feathers.

It was the Serb Savva Lukich Vladislavich (while in Constantinople as an ambassador of Peter I) who bought from the Sultan's seraglio and sent to Russia the black boy Ibrahim (the son of an Abyssinian prince), who was destined to become the great-grandfather of the great poet. Pushkin was proud of his ancestry, both on his father's side and on his mother's side. His words – "It is not only possible, but also necessary to be proud of the glory of your ancestors" – apply to the Balsh, Keshko, Inglezi and many other families of Moldova.

In his three "Kishinev" handwritten notebooks, Pushkin depicted a number of his new acquaintances, among whom one can see noble boyars who came to Bessarabia.

In the beautiful lady in Pushkin's drawing, it is easy to recognize Smaranda Bogdan, if we compare the existing drawing of the poet with the portrait of Smaranda Bogdan from the "Collection of Portraits of the Romanian Academy": the look of large beautiful eyes, a straight little nose, slightly smiling lips, dark curls, a cap.¹⁴ In the same drawing Pushkin depicted another beautiful lady, very similar to Smaranda Bogdan, only younger. Presumably, this is Maria Balsh, the daughter of Smaranda Bogdan, the wife of Todor Balsh. Pushkin often drew relatives together: mother and daughter, husband and wife, sisters, brothers, family.¹⁵

Pushkin drew for himself, he did not sign his drawings, they were not intended for display - therefore, it is very difficult to identify them. This is a whole special science, which the Moldavian Pushkin scholar G. F. Bogach mastered perfectly. On one of the sheets of Pushkin's manuscripts, he saw the Balsh family: Tudora, Maria, Iordache, and a little higher – Alexander (Aleko). A whole series of female and male images in national clothes attracts attention. There is a desire to find out - who are they? Perhaps, Natalia Balsh-Keshko is hiding among these profiles, for example, the beautiful young girl on the right with dark hair, a surprised and tender look.¹⁶ The accuracy of Pushkin's drawings gives them important documentary value, allowing us to imagine with our own eyes what bright historical figures looked like in the 1820.

Pushkin's drawings from the Chisinau period are not just "accompaniments" to the texts, but an independent layer of creativity, reflecting the synthesis of the visual and verbal. They reveal the transformation of the author's method: from literary narrative to laconic form, to impressionistic sketches, experiments with abstraction, to the role of chance, that is, to the use of the methods of 20th century art. This work contributes to the understanding of the phenomenon of Pushkin as a universal artist, whose legacy goes beyond literature, becoming part of world visual culture.

¹³ A.A. Cherkashin, *Family tree of A.S. Pushkin*, 1992, Chisinau: House-museum of A.S. Pushkin.

¹⁴ R. Rosetti, *Familia Rosetti*, București, Collection of portraits of the Romanian Academy, 1938, Vol. I, p. 220. Definition by G. Bogach.

¹⁵ *Workbooks of A.S. Pushkin*. In 8 volumes. St. Petersburg, London, 1995, p. 67. Definition by V. Grabovscaia.

¹⁶ George Bogach, *Deleche of the Northern Capital*, Irkutsk, 1979, p. 17.